

THE ESSENCE OF REFORM IN OUR COUNTRY FOR THE HEALTH OF WOMEN AND CHILDREN

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***Purpose:** to study the reforms carried out in our country to strengthen the reproductive health of the population, protect motherhood and childhood, the birth of a healthy child, the maturation of the physically and spiritually harmonious generation.*

Material and method: in recent years, a number of laws, presidential decrees and resolutions have been adopted aimed at expanding the access of mothers and children to quality medical services, providing them with specialized and high-tech medical care, maintaining reproductive health, preventing the death of infants and children. In this direction, medical services are provided to the population in all regions of the Republic today by perinatal, screening, reproductive health and diagnostic centers, maternity departments, a multidisciplinary Polyclinic, a family polyclinic and rural medical points. In particular, in order to improve the health of women and teenage girls and improve the reproductive health of expectant mothers, improve the quality of medical care for pregnant women, promote maternal health, “women’s consultancies”, girls ‘ health departments have been established in primary medical

institutions. It is also established that the methods of diagnosis, treatment and rehabilitation of gynecological diseases in accordance with modern international requirements are widely applied to practice. work is underway in the health care system to reduce maternal and infant mortality, including early neonatal mortality, underage births.

By the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” dated January 28, 2022, the task of improving the system of high-tech medical care for Reproductive and pregnant women, children, equipping perinatal centers with the necessary medical equipment and supplies, providing them with qualified personnel was established. It would not be an exaggeration to say that this opened the door to a huge change in the health of women and children in our country. At the same time, in remote areas, it is required to establish a high level of targeted care guidance system, improve the effectiveness of the medical care provided to mothers and children, further improve outpatient care, develop emergency and specialized medical care, introduce medical genetics and modern screening programs.

Establishing measures aimed at strengthening the health of mothers and children, creating the necessary conditions for the birth of a healthy child, as well as with representatives of the health sector of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, held on March 18, 2022, “reforms in medicine – as mentioned in the open dialogue on the topic” for the sake of a person " prevention of diseases between mothers and children in the primary unit of the health system, their early identification and introduction into practice of wellness programs, strengthening explanatory work on the issues of the birth, development and upbringing of a healthy child, promoting proper nutrition and increased physical activity,, one of the tasks facing the current health system is to provide pregnant and lactating women with vitamins and minerals for free and to carry out effective prevention of diseases through targeted screening measures, to introduce high-tech and innovative methods

of diagnostics and treatment into practice and to establish a regular increase in the scientific potential of employees of the industry.

Results: since May 1, 2022, the district (city) multidisciplinary central polyclinics, as well as the children's Department in the family polyclinics of the city of Tashkent; in the district (city) medical associations within the current state units, pediatric anesthesiology and resuscitation departments as well as pediatric posts providing emergency medical care day and night; Reference Laboratory for early diagnosis of hereditary-genetic diseases in children at the Republican specialized pediatric scientific and practical Medical Center and the establishment of its 17 regional laboratories in the regions; Republican perinatal Center, Republic of Karakalpakstan, reforms are underway to establish the activities of a total of 29 emergency perinatal and emergency pediatric mobile shift resuscitation brigades in 2022-2023 in the perinatal centers and children's multidisciplinary medical centers of the regions and the city of Tashkent.

Conclusion: the reforms carried out in our country on the health of mothers and children and the medical services provided to them are leading to an improvement in the reproductive health of the population.

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